

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DAMAGE OF DENTAL HARD TISSUES IN PREGNANT WOMEN AND BASIS OF THERAPEUTICAL-PROPHYLACTICAL MEASURES IN GEORGIA

Shinshiashvili T.

*Professor, Tbilisi State Medical University, Georgia
Vazha Pshavela ave. 33*

Zubadalashvili A.

*PhD student, David Aghmashenebeli University of Georgia
Ilia Chavchavadze ave. 25*

Suladze T.

*Assistant Professor, Tbilisi State Medical University, Georgia
Vazha Pshavela ave. 33*

Kvanchakhadze R.

*Professor, David Aghmashenebeli University of Georgia
Ilia Chavchavadze ave. 25*

Manjavidze N.

*Associate professor, Tbilisi State University
Ilia Chavchavadze ave. 1*

Abstract

Despite some sublime halo of future motherhood and belief in physiologic process of pregnancy itself, carrying healthful character for the female organism, the course of pregnancy itself is significant psychoemotional, immunological and metabolic load on female organism. Complicated psychophysiological changes of the organism during pregnancy are accompanied by expressed damage to the condition of oral cavity [1].

Pregnant women are carrying one of the highest risks of developing dental diseases. Main diseases of oral cavity faced by women, are tooth caries and periodontal diseases. One of the problems of pregnancy is the condition of teeth. Even though pregnancy itself is a physiological process, accompanied by its specifics, changes in the hormonal background significantly affects metabolic processes in the organism of future mother [2, 3]. Metabolism of fat, proteins, carbohydrates, and minerals significantly change, which is linked to the formation of new organism. Metabolism of minerals is changed due to the need of higher calcium amount required for the formation of fetal bones, which is extracted from the bone tissues of future mother. Changes in calcium metabolism cause decrease in remineralization properties of saliva.

Normally, enamel strengthening is supported by the actions of calcium and phosphorus contained in the saliva. During pregnancy, their quantity decrease, PH of saliva also decreases, which causes disturbance of acid-base balance of the oral cavity and leads to intensive multiplication of microorganisms, causing caries. According to the studies, such changes in the mineral metabolism weakens density of dental tissues and teeth become weak, easily destructible [4].

Keywords: Pregnant Women, therapeutical-prophylactical measures, dental hard tissues.

Introduction

On the background of changed reactivity and decrease in the resistance of organism in pregnant woman, hidden sources of the infection can lead to serious complications, such as exacerbation of chronic odontogenic sources of infections [5, 6].

Scientific studies and practical experience show that increase in the vulnerability to caries in pregnant women, can have negative results for fetus. High level of caries causing infections in mother can lead to caries formation in babies. [7].

First clinical signs of dental caries in pregnant women appear on sixth-seventh month of pregnancy, which is connected to the peak of skeletal mineralization of the fetus and appearance of calcium deficit in pregnant women. Fetus takes up 80% of calcium during third trimester of pregnancy, causing homeostatic stress in mother's organism. Clinical image worsens with the progression of pregnancy, especially when having toxicosis of the second half of pregnancy [8, 9].

Clinical specifics of caries process, especially during pregnancy with late toxicosis is its acute course. Seldom in pregnant women, especially during early and late toxicosis, increase of dental sensitivity against chemical, thermal and mechanical irritators is remarked, chronic caries process is characterized by asymptomatic course. In pregnant women one may also see non-caries damage of teeth: wedge shaped defects, hyperesthesia of hard tissues, vertical pathological erasability [10].

Prevalence and intensity of dental caries in women increases depending on the quantity of previous pregnancies, with labor outcomes. Along with other factors, disturbance in the concentration of protein and urea, decrease in frequency of salivation, decrease in salivary PH, increase its viscosity, changes in the mineral content of oral fluids have significant effect on pathogenesis of dental caries in pregnant women. During late toxicosis of pregnancy mentioned salivary changes are more expressed [11.,12].

Studies showed that dental diseases in pregnant women arise due to the influence of adverse factors on the organism, removal of which shall be considered during processing regional complex prophylactic programs, methods and means of the prophylactics of dental diseases.

The most effective tool is to plan a prophylactic program based on preliminary situational analysis of dental diseases, considering climatic-geographical, ecological and economical specifics of the country or particular regions. However, lack of general data regarding spread of dental diseases on the territory of Georgia, complicates planning of national as well as regional prophylactic programs. Primarily, this refers to the female population during pregnancy.

Initial manifestations of early forms of dental caries in pregnant women remain poorly studied, intensity of its development and specifics of damage of the dental surface must be considered while planning prophylactic programs, which are more important for Georgia, where the majority of sources of the drinking water is characterized by too low concentration of Fluorides (0.35-0.45 mg/L), [13.,14.]

Despite significant experience in the declared prophylactic direction of healthcare in our country, scientific based prophylactic system of dental diseases in pregnant women is practically not existing, effective prophylactic programs are not included; additionally, creating such programs allows more effective use of potential opportunities of already existing methods and means of prophylaxis.

Considering the above, the aim of the current study is to perform the situational analysis of the diseases of the dental hard tissues in pregnant women, al-

lowing active monitoring of risk-factors in disease development, in order to develop scientific-based therapeutical-prophylactical programs considering the critical periods of pregnancy.

Methods and material

Dental examination of 170 pregnant women aged 18 to 40 years has been conducted, under observation of the dental office in two regional Female consultation centers in Tbilisi (clinic "Gidmed" at N10 Khudadov str. and "Mkurnali" at N87 Ts. Dadiani str.)

During initial examination, each pregnant was informed about character of the study. Data of the primary dental examination was entered in a specifically developed "Card of oral cavity examination in pregnant women", where information about dental status and dynamics during following examinations were added along with passport data, information about obstetric-gynecologic status and specifics of the course of pregnancy were entered as well. All women were examined for 3 times.

During initial address to the dentist, in the second half of pregnancy with gestation age 20-22 weeks and during 34-38 weeks of pregnancy. During late initial visit (after 20 weeks of gestation) they were examined again on 34-38 weeks. Inclusion criteria in the study were pregnant women living in the given climatic-geographic zone. Exclusion criteria were pregnant women with severe extragenital and obstetric pathologies and refusal to participate in the study at any step.

For comparable assessment of the dental hard tissues, efficacy of therapeutical-prophylactic measures and data of obstetric-gynecologic analyses, study participants were divided based on age and term of pregnancy: (Table 1,2)

Table 1

Division of examined pregnant according to age group

Age groups	"Gidmed" clinic	"Mkurnali" clinic	Total %
18-24	34	11	45 (26,47%)
25-33	35	15	70 (41,17%)
34-40	41	14	55 (32,36%)
Total	130	40	170 (100%)

Table 2

Division of pregnant according to gestation age

Gestation age, wks	"Gidmed" clinic	"Mkurnali" clinic	Total %
I trimester (from conception to 13 wk.)	60	13	73 (43%)
II trimester (13-26 wk.)	33	7	40 (23,5%)
III trimester (27-40 wk.)	37	20	57 (33,5%)

Dental examinations were conducted with standard methods: Collection of medical history, examination, probing, percussion. Condition of hard dental tissues were determined by calculating the intensity – CFR, indicator of intensity as sum of teeth with caries (C), teeth with filling (F) and removed teeth (R) of the patient and prevalence (%) of dental caries. Examination of all teeth was performed revealing developing caries process on the stage of spot, with method of intravital staining.

For more precise assessment quantity of caries lesions on different surfaces of the same tooth were considered. Index received during such assessment is marked as CFR.

Hygienic condition of oral cavity were calculated using simplified index Green-Vermilion – ONI-S (Oral Hygiene Indices-simplified), which is a double index and consist of two components: Index of dental plaques – DI-S and index of dental calculi – CI-S. Hygienic index OHI-S is calculated with formula: $OHI-S=(DI-S)+(CI-S)$.

Data are processed statistically using program SPSS-24.

Results and discussion

It is known that during pregnancy quantitative level of mineral materials in saliva decrease, as a result acidity of oral cavity elevate, which leads to acid-base balance disturbance of the oral cavity, and marked increase in the amount of caries causing microorganisms.

As a result, such changes in mineral metabolism decrease density of dental enamel and teeth become weak and vulnerable to the destruction [8].

Study results reflected in the table 3, show massive spread of dental caries among pregnant women and range from 61% to 98.8% ($p < 0.002$). Similar image was characteristic to the index of caries intensity, which was characterized by the increase of CFR with age.

Table 3

Age, Year	“Gidmed” Clinic		“Mkurnali” Clinic	
	Prevalence (%)	CFR Index	Prevalence (%)	CFR Index
18-24	94% $n = 34$	8.74 ± 4.114	61% $n = 11$	2.55 ± 1.036
25-33	98,8% $n = 55$	$11,60 \pm 4.93$	83% $n = 15$	3.13 ± 1.598
34-40	96% $n = 41$	14.31 ± 54.48	91.5% $n = 14$	3.25 ± 1.893
		$p < 0.002$	$p < 0.542$	

It has to be mentioned that among studied patients only 2 (1.17%) were healthy, 11 (6.47%) had compensated form of caries, 29 (17%) had sub-compensated and 128 (75.3%) severe-decompensated form of caries.

Study of specifics of caries development in pregnant, showed defined difference in its manifestation, particularly, caries lesion on one surface was seen in $50 \pm 1.17\%$ cases, two – $32.5 \pm 1.1\%$ and three – $17.5 \pm 0.89\%$ cases. We consider this fact important, as such dynamics of high damage in pregnant women is characteristic to the region, population of which experience fluoride deficit in the water.

According to our studies, clinical specifics of decay process, particularly during late toxicosis of pregnancy, is an acute course, rapid spread not only on peripheries, but to the deepness and pulp of the tooth, which lead to short timelines for development of caries complications; and during stage of stain, enamel stiffness was assessed with probing.

Performed analysis of gestational period and age characteristics in pregnant women who addressed to the dental polyclinic from female consultation, helped to reveal that more or less frequently patients were visiting dentists below age of 25 year on an initial stage of pregnancy. With increase in the gestational term, CFR indicator increased, however maximal index was revealed in the end of second and beginning of the third trimester.

Hygienic condition of oral cavity (according to index OHI-S) in a high percentage of studied pregnant women, was unsatisfactory – mean 62.5%, which was worsening with increase in the term of pregnancy. Hygienic index varied between 2.2-2.6 points in almost half of the observed (48.6%).

As it is known, pregnancy – natural physiologic process, which shall not have a negative effect on the organism, but, unfortunately, due to different reasons, condition of teeth in this period is still worsening. Nausea, vomiting, change in eating habits and worsening of appetite, lead to calcium deficit, which is necessary for fetus, and baby starts taking it and as a result, dental health of mother is worsening.

Change in hormonal background, restructuring of all types of metabolism, including calcium, decrease in the protective forces of organism, change in the function of salivary glands – factors accompanying any pregnancy, at the same time represent the risk factors for developing dental diseases.

There are two reasons revealed during pregnancy causing dental problems: First - hormonal changes of the organism, second is the process of gestation itself, which requires transfer of important microelements from the mother, their deficit is conditioned by metabolic processes during pregnancy. Study of individual cards of pregnant women revealed that 23% of examined had not only deficit of calcium and phosphate but imbalance of these microelements (disturbance Ca/P), which was reflected on the condition of dental system of future mother; in 22% there was deficit in vitamin “D” and 12% - negative iron balance, which was causing iron deficiency anemia. Developing negative balance of iron, calcium, phosphorus, vitamin “D” and other vitamins during pregnancy, affected dental health of pregnant women and as a result severe – decompensated form of caries was diagnosed.

Thus, change in the hormonal background, restructuring all types of metabolism, including calcium, decrease in protective forces of organism, change in the function of salivary glands- these factors, accompanying any pregnancy, at the same time represent risk factors of developing dental diseases, especially for those living in Georgian regions, population who take fluoride deficit water.

Data of our study showed low level of dental health during period of pregnancy, which highlights the necessity for more detailed diagnostics of all risk factors of main dental diseases and realization of all stages of therapeutical-prophylactic measures during period of pregnancy based on the results of full complex examination, considering fluoride deficit situation in our region.

For increase in the level of dental health in pregnant women and getting maximal effect from the taken

anticaries measures the following are required: Therapeutical-prophylactic measures related to caries and its complications considering critical period of pregnancy; Conduct of individually oriented on sanitary-hygienic and dental education.

Conclusion

Pregnancy is a critical period for dental health in women and is characterized by the changes in the level and structure of oral cavity diseases. Currently dental diseases during pregnancy form separate link in cariesology and periodontology based on clinical particularities and effect of general condition of the organism. All these confirm the necessity of more detailed study of the reasons for worsening of dental status in pregnant women, moreover at this moment in Georgia there are no special prophylactic programs for dental diseases during period of pregnancy.

The aim of this study is to conduct situational analysis for diseases of dental hard tissues among pregnant women, allowing to perform active risk-factor monitoring for disease development, and to create science-based therapeutical-prophylactical programs considering critical period of pregnancy.

Study results show massive prevalence of dental caries among pregnant women and comprise 87.8% mean ($p < 0.002$) at intensity of 7,3 and was characterized by increase with age and term of gestation period. Among local risk factors inducing mineralization process of dental hard tissues in all trimesters of the pregnancy, most significant is unsatisfactory hygiene of oral cavity. Index OHI-S in 48.6% of cases comprised 2.2-2.6 points. Between all factors developing during pregnancy, the leading place was taken by negative iron (12%), calcium and phosphorus (23%) balance, vitamin "D" deficiency (22%).

Thus, data of our research showed low level of dental health during period of pregnancy, which highlights necessity for more detailed diagnostics of all risk factors for dental diseases and realization of all stages of therapeutical-prophylactical measures based on the results of full complex examination, considering fluoride deficit situation in Georgia.

References

1. Doucede G., Dehaynin-Toulet E., Kacet L., Jollant B., Tholliez S., Deruelle P., Subtil D. Tooth and pregnancy, a public health issue. *Presse Med.* 2019;48:1043–1050. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
2. Ghareghani M.A.M., Bayani A., Bayat A., Hemmat M., Karimy M., Ahounbar E., Armoon B., Fakhri Y., Schroth R.J. Poor oral health-related quality of life among pregnant women: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int. J. Dent. Hyg.* 2021;19:39–49. doi: 10.1111/idh.12465. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
3. Kurien S., Kattimani V.S., Sriram R.R., Sriram S.K., Bhupathi A., Bodduru R.R., Patil N.N. Management of Pregnant Patient in Dentistry. *J. Int. Oral Health.* 2013;5:88–97. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Armitage G.C. Bi-directional relationship between pregnancy and periodontal disease. *Periodontology* 2000. 2013;61:160–176. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0757.2011.00396.x. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
5. Al Khamis S, Asimakopoulou K, Newton T, Daly B. The effect of dental health education on pregnant women's adherence with toothbrushing and flossing - A randomized control trial. *Community dentistry and oral epidemiology.* 2017;45(5):469–77. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
6. Gontarev S.N., Gontareva I.S., Mostafa Ya sin., Koteneva L.P. Frequency of teeth caries in pregnant women in the starooskol urban district – *Journal of NEW Medical technologies, e Edition – 2019 - №4 – 75-78.*
7. Hussein W., Lafayette R.A. Renal function in normal and disordered pregnancy. *Curr. Opin. Nephrol. Hypertens.* 2014;23:46–53. doi: 10.1097/01.mnh.0000436545.94132.52. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
8. Konopka T., Zakrzewska A. Periodontitis and risk of preeclampsia—A systematic review. *Ginekol. Pol.* 2020;91:158–164. doi: 10.5603/GP.2020.0024. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
9. Lajya Devi Goyal,¹ Dapinder Kaur Bakshi,² Jatinder Kaur Arora,² Ankita Manchanda,³ and Paramdeep Singh⁴ Assessment of fluoride levels during pregnancy and its association with early adverse pregnancy outcomes *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2020 Jun; 9(6): 2693–2698. Published online 2020 Jun 30. doi: 10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_213_20c
10. Ministero Della Salute—Raccomandazioni per la Promozione Della Salute Orale in età Perinatale, Edizione. [(accessed on 1 July 2020)]; Available online: http://www.salute.gov.it/imgs/C_17_pubblicazioni_2317_allegato.pdf
11. Schwartz N., Nachum Z., Green M.S. The prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus recurrence—Effect of ethnicity and parity: A metaanalysis. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* 2015;213:310–317. doi: 10.1016/j.ajog.2015.03.011. [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
12. Schwendicke F., Karimbux N.Y., Allareddy V., Glud C. Periodontal Treatment for Preventing Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes: A Meta- and Trial Sequential Analysis. *PLoS ONE.* 2015;10:e0129060. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0129060. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
13. Tettamanti L. Pregnancy and Periodontal Disease: Does Exist a Two-Way Relationship? *Oral Implant.* 2017;10:112–118. doi: 10.11138/orl/2017.10.2.112. [PMC free article] [PubMed] [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
14. Vilella KD, Fraiz FC, Benelli EM, Assuncao LR. Oral Health Literacy and Retention of Health Information Among Pregnant Women: A Randomised Controlled Trial. *Oralhealth & preventive dentistry.* 2017;15(1):41–8. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]